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Laser patterning on transition metal dichalcogenides thin films

Like graphite, transition metal dichalcogenide (TMDC) bulk crystals are formed of monolayers bound to each other by van-der-Waals attraction. TMDC monolayers have a direct band gap, and can be used in electronics as transistors and in optics as emitters and detectors. However, thickness-limited absorption poses a challenge for high efficiency. To overcome this issue, light-trapping techniques such as patterning is suggested.

The possibility of direct writing structures with a laser on insulating substrates in a clean room-free process is attractive for its simplicity, cost effectiveness and wide choice of substrates allowed, including flexible plastic.

The lithographic set-up consists on a 532 nm laser incorporated to a Raman tool. This together a housemade computer program can also generate periodic patterns of any shape based on lines, dashes and dots, in the form of a set of program instructions. An methodological study about the lithographic process varying laser power and exposure time is realized.

Finally, as proof of concept, an ultrathin superabsorber for all the visible spectra is fabricated based on these nanostructures.